

Mental Health Status of Parents of Children Under Five Years of Age during Covid-19 Pandemic in Guwahati City, Assam

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Received: 25-11-2022 / Revised: 25-12-2022 / Accepted: 21-01-2023

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Background: Today the world is facing an unprecedented situation owing to the effects of COVID-19, an infectious disease caused by SAR-COV-2 virus, with clinical spectrum ranging from asymptomatic to mild respiratory symptoms to rapid death. COVID-19 was first reported in a hospital in Wuhan city, China on 29th Dec 2019. Subsequently the disease spread rapidly throughout the country. The first case of COVID-19 outside of China was confirmed in Thailand in January, 2020. The disease has spread far and wide all over the world effecting almost every country in the world making it a global pandemic. As of now more than 200 million people have been effected across 213 countries and territories leading to loss of lives. As there is no treatment for the novel corona virus till date, lockdown, and social distancing and vaccination is the only practical and safe option to slow down the spread of the virus. Since the onset of the pandemic in early 2020, 35% of the population has experienced mental distress.

Material and Methods: It is a community based cross-sectional study on parents having children from 0-5 years of age. The study was conducted in different municipal wards of Guwahati city, Assam. 5 municipal wards are selected randomly out of which 260 parents will be selected randomly. Based on the previous study "Impact of COVID-19 Outbreak on mental health and perceived strain among the caregivers tending children with special needs" conducted by Sapna Dhiman and Shilpa Jain, School of Psychotherapy, Delhi Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research University, New Delhi India and published in Research in Developmental Disabilities, 6th October 2020. The prevalence of anxiety was found to be 20.5%.

Results: Out of the 260 parents that were interviewed, 77 (29.6%) reported having a family member who was diagnosed with COVID-19, while 183 (70.4%) reported not having any family member who was diagnosed with COVID-19. Among the 87 parents who are govt. sector employees, 79 (90.8%) did not suffer from stress, while 8 (9.2%) suffered from stress. Among the 125 parents who are private sector employees, 93 (74.4%) did not suffer from stress, while 32 (25.6%) suffered from stress. Among the 30 parents who own business, 19 (63.3%) did not suffer from stress, while 11 (36.7%) suffered from stress. Among the 3 parents who reported being involved in agriculture, 2 (66.7%) did not suffer from stress, while 1 (33.3%) suffered from stress. Among the 15 parents who reported being unemployed, 9 (60%) did not suffer from stress, while 6 (40%) suffered from stress.

Conclusion: Thus, through this study, one can conclude that the ongoing pandemic has certainly taken a toll on the mental well-being of parents and as such taking measures to identify and address the issue is the need of the hour. Thus, awareness should be created about identifying signs of various mental health issues so that people can identify and seek necessary medical help at the earliest.

Keywords: Stress-parents-Covid 19.

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Introduction

Today the world is facing an unprecedented situation owing to the effects of COVID-19, an infectious disease caused by SAR-COV-2 virus, with clinical spectrum ranging from asymptomatic to mild respiratory symptoms to rapid death. COVID-19 was first reported in a hospital in Wuhan city, China on 29th Dec 2019. Subsequently the disease spread rapidly throughout the country. The first case of COVID-19 outside of China was confirmed in Thailand in January, 2020. The disease has spread far and wide all over the world effecting almost every country in the world making it a global pandemic. As of now more than 200 million people have been effected across 213 countries and territories leading to loss of lives. As there is no treatment for the novel corona virus till date, lockdown, and social distancing and vaccination is the only practical and safe option to slow down the spread of the virus. Since the onset of the pandemic in early 2020, 35% of the population has experienced mental distress. The danger of a global mental health crisis was discussed early in the pandemic due to manifold restrictions and changes in daily living: confrontation with death, fear of contracting the virus or transmitting it to others, isolation during quarantine, financial strain, job loss, anger against measures, closed public facilities, and visitation bans to relatives [1].

COVID-19 has posed new threats to families through social isolation due to physical distancing measures, childcare closures, financial and employment

insecurities, housing instability and changes to health and social care access. These shifts have profoundly interrupted the systems and structures that previously operated to support both the mental health (anxiety, depression and perceived stress) and well-being of the parents, specifically having children belonging to 0-5 years of age and mitigate the risks that contribute to health and social inequities. Other factors include marital issues, family harmony and conflicts, parents' history of mental illness and parenting style. Parents have faced myriad stress from loss of economic and psychological support for their children. Stressors and needs within families with young children may differ from those of other household types, where childcare obligations or home schooling can be serious challenges that are unique to parents [2] In addition parents with children disproportionately live in poverty, potentially increasing the risk of economic distress through acute job loss and relative difficulties sustaining basic needs such as food security and reliable child care. Parents who were able to work from home, juggling ongoing work obligations also face challenges around establishing a new work routine and creating a workspace conducive to productivity while balancing childcare duties Parents who have lost their jobs found themselves having to manage childcare while struggling to address new financial concerns and economic stress related to inability to work and/or job loss. Moreover, parents are neglecting their normal daily routines. As a result, children tend to follow same

haphazard habits and routines. Thus, it has become socially difficult for parents to maintain a strict routine for the children- fix times for meals, studying and sleeping.

Globally, nurseries and childcare closures have added personal parental pressures to balance responsibilities including becoming the sole providers of supervision and education for their children- all while experiencing emotional stress. Many parents are not equipped with proper teaching resources and some other are illiterate to teach their own children. As a result, children are missing out on an important phase of their learning journey and overall development. With a considerable dip in COVID-19 cases, many states across the country have eased COVID-19 related restrictions. However, these relaxations have created havoc among the parents about health risk of returning to populated spaces and exposure to the virus while at work and during travel to and from work. One of the consequences of this pandemic was the suspension or slowing down of vaccination campaigns in almost all the countries. However, there is a need to assess anxiety related to the COVID-19 pandemic among parents. To our knowledge, only one scale was developed to assess parenting during a pandemic ; however, it has not yet been validated in a parent sample. [3]

Parents lacked clarity around whether vaccination services were operating as usual and feared around contracting COVID-19 while attending general practices. In addition to the stress caused by the pandemic, the parent-child relationship and the relationship between parents also affect the mental health of parents in such a difficult period, and parents' mental health can further effects children's mental and physical health creating a vicious circle. Parenting stress may be a better indicator of COVID-19-related impacts than a general family functioning measure, which may have a more distal relationship [4]. Contemporary

research has provided some evidence of the interconnected anxiety of parents and their children during pandemics , which could prompt a parent-based intervention approach to simultaneously address fears and burden in families. [5]

Material and Methods

Study Design: It is a community based cross-sectional study.

Study Area: The study was conducted in different municipal wards of Guwahati city, Assam.

Study Period: The study was conducted between October and November 2021 .

Study Population: Parents having children from 0-5 years of age.

Sampling Technique: 5 municipal wards are selected randomly out of which 260 parents will be selected randomly.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Parents having children from 0-5 years of age
2. Parents residing within Guwahati city.
3. Parents willing to participate in the study.

Exclusion criteria

1. Parents residing in Guwahati city for less than 6 months.
2. Parents diagnosed with any psychological disease before.

Sample Size: Based on the previous study "Impact of COVID-19 Outbreak on mental health and perceived strain among the caregivers tending children with special needs" conducted by Sapna Dhiman and Shilpa Jain, School of Psychotherapy, Delhi Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research University, New Delhi India and published in Research in Developmental Disabilities, 6th October 2020. The prevalence of anxiety was found to be 20.5%.

The sample size will be calculated based on the formula:

$$Z = 4PQ/L^2$$

Here,

Z = sample size

P = prevalence = 20.5%

Q = 1 - prevalence = 79.5%

L = relative error = 5%.

After doing the calculation, Z will be 260.76, rounding off to 260. The sample size for the study will be 260.

Data Collection Tool: The data were collected by interviewing the parents of children between 0-5 years of age. These questions will be based on DASS-21.

Data Collection Technique: To obtain the target sample size, 5 Municipal wards from Guwahati city will be selected randomly. In these wards families will be selected randomly which have children from 0-5 yrs of age. To carry out the study, a qualitative way is to be used for sampling. Selected parents will be interviewed using a pre-designed and pretested questionnaire. The questions will be elaborate, self-explanatory. Incomplete and random responses will be deleted, the valid responses are assessed and the final number of responses are analyzed for the study. Before the study, informed verbal consent will be taken by the project group.

Statistical Analysis: Computer applications like Microsoft Word and Microsoft Excel were used for typing, tabulating and for making a graphical presentation of the data collected.

Results

Out of the 260 parents that were interviewed, 77 (29.6%) reported having a family member who was diagnosed with COVID-19, while 183 (70.4%) reported not having any family member who was diagnosed with COVID-19.

Among the 87 parents who are govt. sector employees, 79 (90.8%) did not suffer from stress, while 8 (9.2%) suffered from stress. Among the 125 parents who are private sector employees, 93 (74.4%) did not suffer from stress, while 32 (25.6%) suffered from stress. Among the 30 parents who own business, 19 (63.3%) did not suffer from stress, while 11 (36.7%) suffered from stress. Among the 3 parents who reported being involved in agriculture, 2 (66.7%) did not suffer from stress, while 1 (33.3%) suffered from stress. Among the 15 parents who reported being unemployed, 9 (60%) did not suffer from stress, while 6 (40%) suffered from stress.

Table 1: Association of Covid 19 infection in the family with parental stress

Covid 19 Diagnosis in the family	Normal	Stress	Total
Yes	52(67.5%)	25(32.5%)	77
No	150(82%)	33(18%)	183
Total	202	58	260
p-value	0.011		

Table 1 shows that there is significant association between diagnosis of COVID-19 in the family and stress since $p = 0.011 < 0.05$.

Table 2: Association of Family structure with Parental anxiety

Family Structure	Normal	Anxiety	Total
nuclear	130(77.4%)	38(22.6%)	168
Joint	88(95.7%)	4(4.3%)	92
Total	218	42	260
p-value	0.0001		

Table 2 shows Anxiety was found to be more in parents who live in a nuclear family. There is significant association

between family structure and anxiety since $p = 0.0001 < 0.05$.

Among the 172 parents who reported that their child(ren) go (es) to school, 131 (76.2%) did not suffer from stress, while 41 (23.8%) suffered from stress. Among the 88 parents who reported that their child(ren) do (es) not go to school, 71 (80.7%) did not suffer from stress, while 17 (19.3%) suffered from stress.

Discussion

In our study, mental morbidity was found significantly higher in unemployed parents. Research from prior economic downturns shows that job loss is associated with increased depression, anxiety, distress, and low self-esteem and may lead to higher rates of substance use disorder and suicide. During the pandemic, adults in households with job loss or lower incomes report higher rates of symptoms of mental illness than those without job or income loss. Loss of jobs during the pandemic has increased the uncertainty variable amongst the parents as now they are not only worried for the well-being and normal growth of their children but also they are stressed about the survival of the family as a whole.

In a study by Dana Alonzo et Al [6], it was found that the pandemic affected the mental wellbeing of parents more than non-parents especially in low-income high-risk communities. In our study, it was observed that yearly income of parents significantly affected their mental health. Parents who belong to lower socioeconomic groups are also worried about future lockdowns, as they either become unemployed during lockdowns or are underpaid. The COVID-19 pandemic and the resulting economic recession have negatively affected many people's mental health and created new barriers for people already suffering from mental illness.

Among the 77 parents who reported having a family member who was diagnosed with COVID-19, 69 (89.6%) did not suffer from anxiety, while 8 (10.4%) suffered from anxiety. Among the

183 parents who reported not having any family member who was diagnosed with COVID-19, 149 (81.4%) did not suffer from anxiety, while 34 (18.6%) suffered from anxiety. A similar study is done Wu, Mengting, et al [7] where the detected rates of depression and anxiety in parents were 6.1% and 4.0%. The depression, anxiety and perceived stress of parents in central China were significantly higher than those in non-central China. The anxiety of college students' parents was lower than that of parents of the primary, middle and high school students. The depression, anxiety and perceived stress of parents with conflicts in the family were significantly higher than those with a harmonious family.

The study points to concerns around poor mental health and well-being for parents, particularly mothers, as many are experiencing challenges with lack of childcare, especially mothers of nuclear families who do not have any support in childcare. During lockdown when childcare homes were closed and the children were 24-hour responsibility of the parents, joint families offered a relief to the parents as stress and anxiety were found to be significantly high in nuclear families as compared to joint families and hence the role of social support structure cannot be denied. Though not significant, the mental state was slightly poor in the parents of children who go to school, this may be due to the fact that the parents are also concerned about the education of their children as starting their education journey from an online platform may not be as reliable as physical classes. Our study also indicates towards poor mental health of parents in households where there has been a prior COVID-19 diagnosis. This can be attributed to the fact that there has been such misinformation about the whole pandemic situation that it creates unnecessary panic and often leads

Conclusion

Families across the globe are adapting to changes due to (COVID-19) and fear, uncertainty and being holed up at home is likely to take a toll on the mental health of parents and caregivers in the family making them susceptible to issues like stress, depression and anxiety. As such, our study aimed at assessing the impact of the pandemic on the mental health of 260 parents (with children aged between 0-5 years) across 13 wards in Kamrup Metro. It was found that of the 260 parents interviewed, 10% showed signs of depression, 16.2% showed signs of anxiety and 22.3% showed signs of stress. Factors such as the income, nature of employment of the parent and family structures were the major factors responsible for the deteriorating mental health status of parents while the status of the child's schooling seemed to have no significant association with the same. Thus, through this study, one can conclude that the ongoing pandemic has certainly taken a toll on the mental well-being of parents and as such taking measures to identify and address the issue is the need of the hour. Thus, awareness should be created about identifying signs of various mental health issues so that people can identify and seek necessary medical help at the earliest.

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